

Perception towards crypto currency : A study in Indian context.

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Abstract

Crypto currency is the revolutionary innovation used cryptography for security, operates without any centralized authority. Crypto currency is an alternative for investment with high return and risk. High return attracted several investors and policy makers but lack of awareness of technology and misconception hampered the growth of the currency in India . People are aware of the currency , at least heard it but hesitate to invest due to misconception about the currency. The present study analyzed the perception of crypto currency on basis of several factors identified from pervious literature. Primary data has been collected through questionnaire framed on basis of past literature . Factors are identified and validated by applied factor analysis. 254 responses has been collected and only 221 respondents are taken for further analysis. Various statistical tools such as factor analysis, mean, S.D, has been used to analysis the data . The present research concluded that risk factor and regulation factors are more crucial and policy makers should dealt it with first.

Keywords

Crypto Currency, Perception, Block Chain Technology, Cryptography, Risk, Factor Analysis, Regulation.

Introduction

Concept of Crypto currency

Crypto currencies operates without any centralized authority used cryptography to record data. The currency used block chain technology and enables peer to peer transactions verified by network nodes and record in digital ledger . Miners add new block in the block chain by solving complex problems , maintain security and receive rewards for this.

" A crypto currency is a peer to peer digital currency system that uses cryptographic techniques to secure transactions and control the creation of new units"- **Nakamoto,S. (2008): A Peer-to-Peer Electronic Cash system**

FATF (Financial Action Task Force) defines a virtual currency " a digital representation of value that can be digitally traded and functions as (1) a medium of exchange; and/or (2) a unit of account; and/or (3) a store of value, but does not have legal tender status (i.e., when tendered to a creditor, is a valid and legal offer of payment) in any jurisdiction."

According to Indian Law, (Finance Bill 2022), The Indian legal definition of crypto currency, as of the Finance Bill 2022, . A VDA is defined as "any information, code, number, or token generated through cryptographic means, providing a digital representation of value with inherent or stored value".

Need for the Study:

Crypto currency witnessed significant growth in last years but still people hesitate to invest in the currency because of unclear regulations risk of security, volatility in prices . These factors necessitate that research should be conducted to know the perception of people about the currency. The present research will help the policy makers and investors to understand the problems faced by people in rural and semi urban cities.

Objective of study

1. To examine the awareness level of crypto currency
2. To analysis the perception level of stakeholders towards crypto currency older towards crypto currency.

Review of Literature

Alka &Amit (2026) studied the awareness level of respondents on basis of primary date collected through questionnaire and concluded that people are aware of crypto currency as

result shows that 92.5% of total respondents are aware of crypto currency but in depth knowledge is still very low and Bitcoin is the most popular currency as 89% of respondents knows about Bit coin.

Asma &Al-Mothana (2025) examined the perception of under graduate students towards flipped learning approach and applied likert scale and mean,S,D for interpretation.

Mythili et al. (2025) have analyzed the perception of investors of Coimbatore city towards crypto currency .The study is based on both primary and Secondary data as primary data has been collected through questionnaire and secondary data from various books, secondary reports and from several web sites and research articles. Several statistical test such as Chi-square test, regression , Anova has been used for analysis.

Dawa et al. (2024) have studied and analyzed the perception level to adopt crypto currency Primary data has been collected from the students of Royal University of Bhutan through questionnaire and applied TAM model for analysis , concluded that students of University are aware of crypto currency but not want to invest due to lack of clear regulations.

Ramprakash et al. (2023) have studied the factors that influence the adoption of crypto currency for digital payments. Data has been collected through purposive sampling, used multiple regression for analysis , concluded that social attitude and positive social influence are important element for adoption of crypto currency.

Sharan et al. (2023) analyzed the attitude of young people towards crypto currency investment The study is based on both primary and secondary sources and various statistical techniques such as correlation, regression, and chi-square tests has been applied for analysis. The study concluded that investment by young people in crypto currency has been increased due to low cost and motivated by the risk-taking psychology of the younger generation.

Chary et al. (2022) recognized occupation, education, social media product price, social status, and working environment as most crucial factors for investing in crypto currency. Primary data that has been collected from businessman via questionnaire and secondary data from various sources analyzed by using multiple correlation techniques,

Doshi (2020) studied the views of stakeholders on future of crypto currency in India .The study is based on primary data , concluded that big and urban area investors are more positive in comparison to small investors and future of crypto currency is bright and have more opportunities in future.

Othman & Othman (2015) examined the “relationship between entrepreneurial intentions and entrepreneurial career choice behavior among Malaysian university students” and applied mean and S.D. for analysis and men interpretation were adopted from (Norasmah,2002) as Mean Score Level 1.00–2.00 (Low), 2.01–3.00 (Moderately Low), 3.01–4.00 (Moderately High) and 4.01–5.00(High).

Karthik & Anjaneyulu (2022) analyzed the entrepreneurship behaviors of MBA students in the state universities in Telangana state and applied mean and S.D for analysis ,interpretate the mean score as 1.00 to 2.00 (low), 2.01 to 3.00 (Medium low), 3.01 to 4.00(Medium high), 4.01 to 5.00 (high) according to Norasmah Othman scale.

Methodology

Research design is the plan that explains the process of conducting research to achieve the objectives of the study.

Sampling design: The framework and design describes the method of sampling, sample size ,selection process adopted for the study.

Type of data: Primary data has been collected for analysis in the study by sending questionnaire and factors are identified on basis of previous literature and validated through factor analysis. Responses are collected through Questionnaire circulated through Google form links from selected respondents.

Sampling units: District Sirsa and Hisar are taken for the study and sampling units includes the respondents who have heard about crypto currency and selected from various educational backgrounds and areas.

Sample size: Samples are selected on basis of feasibility, convenience, and topic limitation. Out of 400 respondents, only 253 respondents have given responses, 15 responses are eliminated due to inconsistent responses and outliers. Out of 239 respondents, only 221 respondents have

heard about crypto currency. The present study selected only 221 respondents for further analysis.

Analysis:

Awareness of crypto currency

Have you heard about crypto currency? (basic awareness)

Table 6.1

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	221	92.5	92.5	92.5
	No	18	7.5	7.5	100.0
	239	100.0	100.0		

The above tables clearly shows that out of 239 respondents, only 221 respondents have heard about crypto currency

Chart 6.1

The above chart clearly shows that 92.5% of respondents have heard about crypto currency clearly indicate that awareness is high in India.

Are you familiar with the underlying technology behind crypto currencies(block chain technology) (Depth of awareness)

Table 6.2

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very Familiar	34	14.2	14.2	14.2
	Somewhat Familiar	125	52.3	52.3	66.5
Not Familiar at all	80	33.5	33.5	100.0	
	239	100	100		

Chart 6.2

Awareness is high but still people have no knowledge about technology behind crypto currency as only 14.2% said very familiar

Type of Crypto Currency

Table 6.3

	Currency	Percent of Cases
Valid	Bitcoin	89.0%
	Ethereum	29.2%
Ripple	12.7%	
Litecoin	13.6%	
None of above	17.4%	

Chart 6.3

Above chart clearly demonstrate popularity of Bit coin as 89% respondents knows about Bit coin, 29.20% of respondents said that they have knowledge of Ethereum and 17.40% of respondent said that they don't know about any currency.

Perception of Crypto Currency:

As from above results, it is clear that awareness level is high but still people are not investing in the crypto currency due to perception relation to regulations and risk. Perception is defined as multidimensional conduct, as many factors such as risk, regulation, technological knowledge and psychological beliefs are attach with it. The present study measure the perception of crypto currency through primary data has been conducted through questionnaire . Liket 5 point scale has been used to know the perception and Cronbach’s Alpha has been used to check the reliability of the data. Overall reliability .884 confirmed the suitability of data for analysis. The factors are identified in questionnaire and Exploratory Factor analysis was applied to validate the factors.KMO(Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin also found above the recommended level and Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity was also found to be significant($p < 0.05$) highly support the suitability of data for factor analysis. Eigenvalues are greater than one are extracted and the retained items shows loading above .40

Reliability Statistics

Overall reliability

Table 6.4

Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Items
.884	21

Factor wise Reliability:

Table 6.5

Factor	Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Items
Risk Factor	.869	5
Psychological Factor	.856	6
Social Factor	.869	4
Regulatory Factor	.841	3
Technological Factor	.735	3

The above table shows the result of reliability analysis , has been conducted for internal consistency of likert scale . Cronbach's Alpha for all statement is .884 and also for each factor is at suitable level, indicate the reliability of data for further analysis.

Factor Analysis

Table 6.6

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.865	
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	2308.263

	Df	210
Sig.	.000	

Rotated Component Matrix

Table 6.7

Component

1 2 3 4 5

RP1		.799			
RP2		.760			
RP3		.820			
RP4		.750			
RP5		.783			
REG1				.768	
REG2				.823	
REG3				.819	
TEC1					.673
TEC2					.805
TEC3					.745
SOC1			.781		
SOC2			.788		
SOC4			.883		
SOC5			.851		
PSY1	.627				
PSY2	.608				
PSY3	.759				
PSY4	.773				
PSY5	.701				
PSY6	.757				

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

The factors were defined in questionnaire at early stage on basis of previous literature and Exploratory factor analysis with varimax rotation was applied to validate the predefined factor structure with K-M-O test and also applied Bartlett’s test of sphericity which confirmed the suitability of data for factor analysis. The rotated component matrix clearly demonstrate that most of the statements loaded on their predefined factors as loading above 0.40. The results clearly depict the validity, reliability of construct and indicate that conceptual dimensions which are identified from previous literature are statistically valid.

Table 6.8*

Statement code	Statement	Mean	S.D	Mean score interpretation
RP1	Investment in cryptocurrency is risky	4.16	.832	High
RP2	Ambiguity in cryptocurrency regulations increases risk	4.12	.777	High
RP3	Cryptocurrency uncertain future makes it too risky	4.09	.877	High
RP4	Concerned about the volatility of crypto currency prices	3.94	.815	Moderate High
RP5	Higher risk for losing money as compare to traditional investment	4.11	.952	High
REG1	Clear regulations would boost my confidence in investing in cryptocurrency	4.15	.771	High
REG2	Effective regulatory framework results in minimize of fraud and scam	4.11	.807	High
REG3	Regulations enhanced legal acceptance of cryptocurrency	4.12	.795	High
TEC1	Decentralized blockchain technology in crypto ensures security and transparency	3.78	.775	Moderate High
TEC2	More advanced technology compare to traditional investment	3.86	.694	Moderate High

TEC3	Blockchain makes crypto transactions more safer than traditional payments	3.70	.781	Moderate High
SOC1	Prefer due to recommendations of family/friend	3.57	.977	Moderate High
SOC2	Recommendations of my friends and family boost my confidence to invest	3.50	.942	Moderate High
SOC4	Positive views by celebrities influence me for investment	3.23	1.126	Moderate High
SOC5	Social media also influence my view of crypto currency	3.42	1.112	Moderate High
PSY1	Regulatory framework in crypto currency is less effective than traditional investments	3.81	.849	Moderate High
PSY2	Feel comfortable to investment in traditional investments	3.78	.908	Moderate High
PSY3	Prefer tangible investment over digital assets like cryptocurrency	3.71	.944	Moderate High
PSY4	More risky to invest than traditional investment	3.81	.872	Moderate High
PSY5	Cryptocurrency provides limited options for portfolio diversification	3.55	.960	Moderate High
PSY6	Cryptocurrency is less reliable than traditional investment	3.69	.933	Moderate High

(*Mean Score Level 1.00-2.00 Low, 2.01-3.00 Moderately Low, 3.01-4.00 Moderately High, 4.01-5.00 High retrieved from the previous studies(Entrepreneurial Behaviour of Business Management Students in Telangana State by Neeradi Karthik & Dr. CH. Anjaneyulu based on Norasmah (2002), pp202)

Above table clearly shows the respondents perception of crypto currency. The mean value of individual statements related to risk, regulations, technological knowledge clearly indicate that these factors influence the perception related to crypto currency.

Statement wise Mean

Factor 1 (RISK FACTOR)

The means value of each statement (Risk Factor) is 4 indicate clearly shows that respondents believed that risk factor is most crucial for investment in crypto currency

Factor 2 (Regulatory Factor)

Each statement of regulatory factor have mean value is close to 4 clearly demonstrate that regulatory factor is also very crucial and more important and should be dealt with.

Factor 3 (Technological Factor)

The third factor of the study is technological factor which is validated from factor analysis indicate the importance of technological knowledge as mean value of each statement of the factor less than risk and regulatory factor shows that technical knowledge on crypto currency is important but less crucial from risk factor and regulatory factor.

Factor 4 (Psychological Factor)

The mean value of each individual statements of the psychological factor is 3.81, 3.78, 3.71, 3.81, 3.55 & 3.69) demonstrate the moderate perception reflects that people still believe in traditional investments and hesitate to invest in crypto currency.

Factor 5 (Social Factor)

Mean value of each statement of the social factor also shows moderate perception towards crypto currency.

Table 6.9

Sr. No	Factor	No. of items	Mean	S.D.	Perception level
1	Risk Factor	5	4.0833	.69094	High
2	Psychological factor	6	3.7247	.69560	Moderate
3	Regulatory Factor	3	4.1267	.68905	High
4	Tech. Factor	3	3.7813	.60714	Moderate
5	Social Factor	4	3.4299	.88302	Moderate

The results from above table demonstrate that mean and S.D of combined mean varies from moderate to high perception(based on the). High mean of regulatory factor and risk factor shows that people are more concerned about regulatory aspects and risk factor. Psychological, social & technological factor are less crucial comparison to risk and regulatory factor.

Findings

1. Bitcoin is the most popular crypt currency for investment
2. 92.3% of respondents are aware and 7.5% are unaware of crypto currency
3. Awareness level is high in total but in depth awareness of technology is very low as only 14.2% of respondents are very familiar to the currency
4. Social media is the most popular source for information related to crypto currency
5. Risk factor and regulatory factors are more crucial for investment in crypto currency.

Conclusion

As awareness of crypto currency is increased day by day but still don't invest in the crypto currency due to lack of financial literacy ,unclear regulations and price volatility. Present study results indicate that people have heard about crypto currency but they don't have any knowledge technology behind it. The results of the study indicate that risk and regulation factor are more crucial and have to be dealt with it. The study suggested that there should be more education programs related to crypto currency ,financial literacy moves should focus on risk, regulation and security aspects as these are the most crucial aspects for crypto investments. Policy makers should focus on reliable information and ensures that this information should be

easily accessible to general public. Clear regulation make it as Economic indicator like stock market and it can serve as a new investment alternative in the future.

Suggestions for the future Study

1. Investors should analysis the market before investing
2. Investors should understand the risk factor involved with investment
3. Strict KYC norms should be there to avoid the fraud
4. Clear instruction for various trading platforms should be there.

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